

CHINA'S FOREIGN POLICY TOWARDS CENTRAL ASIA

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Abstract: This article provides a comprehensive analysis of China's foreign policy approach towards the Central Asian region, with a particular emphasis on its engagement with Uzbekistan. The piece examines the multifaceted drivers underpinning China's strategic pivot towards the Central Asian sphere, encompassing economic, diplomatic, and security considerations. Economically, the article elucidates how China leverages its relationships with states like Uzbekistan to bolster its energy security and continental trade connectivity through initiatives such as the Belt and Road. Diplomatically, China seeks to cultivate stable, cooperative partnerships in Central Asia to counter Western influence and secure a quiescent periphery. From a security standpoint, the region's proximity to China's restive Xinjiang province has prompted deepened counterterrorism collaboration between China and its Central Asian neighbors, including Uzbekistan. The analysis also explores the complexities and potential pitfalls of China's burgeoning influence in Central Asia, including concerns surrounding debt traps and the potential erosion of regional autonomy. The article underscores how Uzbekistan, in particular, has navigated this delicate balance by pursuing a multi-vector foreign policy that engages with China, Russia, and the West.

Key Words: China's Foreign Policy, Central Asia, Uzbekistan, economic integration, Belt and Road Initiative.

Introduction

Currently, China is a pivotal political partner for the nations of Central Asia. Since the establishment of the People's Republic of China, the development of the country's foreign policy has traversed several distinct phases. Under the stewardship of Deng Xiaoping (commonly referred to as the second generation of leaders), China presented a novel foreign policy persona on the international stage, one that was markedly divergent from the previous iteration, defined by the legacy of Mao Zedong. Consequently, the contemporary foreign policy of China should be examined through the prism of Deng Xiaoping's transformative reform efforts.

Each subsequent leadership has propounded its own unique conceptual framework, yet a certain continuity has persisted in both domestic and external policy spheres. However, at every new stage of China's foreign policy strategy development, novel approaches to the analysis of international dynamics have also emerged. Therefore, an evolutionary perspective in the examination of the progression of China's contemporary foreign policy contributes to a more nuanced understanding and assists in forecasting future shifts in China's foreign policy orientation. Additionally, in order to delve deeply and comprehensively into the core conceptual tenets of Chinese foreign policy, the judicious application of comparative analysis and historical reminiscence proves invaluable.

Main part

Navigating the post-soviet landscape

For an extended period during the existence of the USSR, China continued to recognize the pivotal role of Russia in the region. In this context, it is unsurprising that the dissolution of the Soviet Union necessitated an urgent recalibration of China's foreign policy strategy towards the Central Asian region. It is worth noting that the rapid process of independence gained by the Central Asian states, coupled with the parallel withdrawal of Russia from the region, came as a significant surprise to the Chinese leadership.

In the wake of these events, China's primary interests centered on issues of national and regional security, which could potentially impact the Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region (XUAR) in the near future. Among these, the Civil War in Tajikistan and the precarious situation in Afghanistan were of particular concern. However, China still lacked a well-defined strategy for Central Asia, compelling its authorities to adopt a more situational approach.

Among the initial steps in China's regional diplomacy, one can identify the following: 1) the establishment of diplomatic relations with the newly-formed states; 2) the resolution of various disputes (such as territorial ones) inherited from the Soviet era; and 3) negotiations regarding Uyghur separatism, which posed a grave threat to China's territorial integrity. These efforts culminated in the formation of a comprehensive contractual and legal framework governing China's relations with the Central Asian republics. By early 1992, China had established diplomatic ties with Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan.

Given that the primary agenda for China in Central Asia was the security of the XUAR, in particular, and China's western borders, in general, the most active development of relations occurred with Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan, as these

countries share an extensive land border with China. Additionally, these states host sizeable Uyghur diasporas (exceeding 300,000 individuals). Unsurprisingly, discussions regarding disputed territories and border delineation between China and these two countries commenced as early as 1992.

In the early 1990s, economic cooperation with the countries of Central Asia was not a priority direction of the foreign policy of the People's Republic of China. The value of trade turnover between the countries of the region and China during the period of 1992-1995 fluctuated at the level of 350-520 million dollars. The main trade partners of China in the region remained Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan, as only they had direct transport communication with China, which allowed them to have a monopoly on the trade of Chinese goods in the region.

During this initial period, China's relations with the states of Central Asia developed in a bilateral format, which allowed fairly quickly and effectively addressing the security issues that were on the agenda at that time, as well as having a clear understanding of the situation in each individual country.

However, as early as October 1992, a working group (4+1) was established in Minsk, whose task was to resolve the border issue. It included China, Russia, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, and Tajikistan. Subsequently, this association became the foundation for the establishment in 1996 of an interstate organization called the "Shanghai Five"⁴.

Thus, in the first half of the 1990s, the People's Republic of China (PRC) pursued a rather cautious policy in the Central Asian region, merely observing its prospective partners and assessing potential risks and threats. Despite the apparent "indecisiveness" that many perceived, it was during this period that the foundations were laid for the further development and deepening of China's relations with the Central Asian republics, not only in the sphere of security, but also in the realm of political and economic cooperation.

In the second half of the 1990s, the PRC embarked on a re-evaluation of its foreign policy towards the region. This was facilitated by factors such as the Taiwan issue, the escalation of tensions with the United States, and the financial crisis in Southeast Asia. China was also concerned about the formation of a unipolar international system dominated by the US.

⁴ Agreement between the Republic of Kazakhstan, the Kyrgyz Republic, the Russian Federation, the Republic of Tajikistan, and the People's Republic of China on Strengthening Trust in the Military Sphere in the Border Area, signed on April 26, 1996 http://base.spininform.ru/show_doc.fwx?rgn=3879

Gradually, Beijing began to formulate a new foreign policy strategy for China in the context of increasing globalization, with the aim of attaining the "status of a great power that structures the international system," "supporting favorable external conditions for Chinese reforms," and "impeding efforts to hinder China's rise".⁵

From now on, China is embarking on an active foreign policy towards Central Asia. By this point, the main threats had become apparent - extremism, terrorism, Islamic radicalism, Uyghur separatism, drug trafficking, nationalism, and others, which had deeply concerned all the states in the region. China was particularly concerned about the trend of growing Uyghur separatism, which was actively manifesting both in the region and in the western part of the Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region (XUAR). Another issue troubling China was the situation around Afghanistan, which was gradually turning into a zone of constant military operations.

At the same time, China began to clearly delineate its interest in the energy resources of the region. In the mid-1990s, Central Asia turned out to be the second "Persian Gulf" in terms of the explored volume of oil and gas. The growing energy needs of the Chinese economy actualized the problem of China's entry into the raw material markets of the Central Asian region.

In 2000, China adopted the "Great Western Development" strategy, which paid great attention to Central Asia. The resource-rich region, according to the plans of the Chinese authorities, should contribute to the accelerated development of the western regions of China. This should solve the problem of the economic lag of the western and central regions behind the coastal territories. Furthermore, within the framework of this strategy, the XUAR is positioned as a springboard for the promotion of Chinese goods and services into the Central Asian market.⁶

To address these tasks and transition to a new, more advanced level of relations, in 1996, on the initiative of China and Russia, a new interstate platform called the "Shanghai Five" was established on the basis of the "4+1" working group, which included Russia, China, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Tajikistan. Later, in accordance with the Declaration of June 15, 2001, the Shanghai Cooperation Organization was established on its basis⁷, with the PRC occupying a leading position.

⁵ Momonov, M.V. The "Prevention of danger" strategy in China's foreign policy // International Trends (Russia). - 2007. - No. 3. - P. 28-43.

⁶ Wang Chaolin, Savkovich E.V. The formation of a development belt in the Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region of the PRC in the early 2010s // Bulletin of Tomsk State University. History. - 2018. - No. 55. - P. 95.

⁷ "Declaration on the Establishment of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization" (SCO), which was signed on June 15, 2001.

At the outset, the paramount concerns for the SCO member states revolved around matters of security and defense cooperation. Simultaneously, the ongoing negotiations on the demarcation of the borders between China and Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Tajikistan progressed, culminating in the finalization of respective agreements in 1996 and 1997, signed in Shanghai and Moscow respectively.

Military cooperation was invigorated after the Islamic Movement of Uzbekistan (IMU) militants attempted to infiltrate the territories of Uzbekistan and Kyrgyzstan in 1999-2000. Collaboration was established between the military and law enforcement agencies, with China providing military assistance to the Central Asian countries. Thus, within a relatively short period, China managed to acquire the status of an equal partner to Russia in the region, becoming one of the guarantors of security.

The September 11, 2001 terrorist attacks and the subsequent global events (the wars in Iraq and Afghanistan, and the parallel process of American presence expansion in the region) threatened the stability in Central Asia and prompted China to embark on a policy of defending its interests in the region. The main emphasis was placed on strengthening the dialogue between the countries through the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO). The primary objectives of the SCO were 1) to enhance stability and security across the expansive territory encompassing the member states, including the Central Asian region, 2) to combat terrorism, separatism, extremism, and drug trafficking, and 3) to develop economic cooperation, energy partnerships, and scientific and cultural interactions.

Since 2006, China has increasingly advocated for the expansion of economic cooperation within the SCO framework. Beijing proposed the establishment of a free trade zone and a regional transportation network. The 2008-2009 global financial crisis further accentuated the prominence of economic and investment-related issues in China's relations with Central Asia.

In recent years, China has been actively lobbying for the construction of major railway infrastructure projects. One such project is the "China - Kyrgyzstan - Uzbekistan" railway line. This proposed transnational railway is intended to connect the existing Chinese railway network to Uzbekistan, and then extend further westward through the territories of Afghanistan, Iran, and Turkey, ultimately linking up with the European railway network.

The motivations behind China's push for this ambitious transcontinental rail project are multifaceted. On the surface, the project appears to be driven by China's primarily peaceful economic interests in the region. By establishing this direct rail link between China and Europe, bypassing the maritime route, China aims to

facilitate the more efficient and cost-effective movement of goods and resources. This aligns with China's broader strategy of developing overland trade and transportation corridors as part of its "Belt and Road Initiative."

However, a deeper analysis suggests that China's interests in this region go beyond just commercial considerations. The region of Central Asia, which would be traversed by this railway, is rich in natural resources that China seeks to access and leverage to address its own domestic development needs and challenges. By establishing greater connectivity and influence in Central Asia through infrastructure projects like this railway, China appears to be positioning itself to better harness the resource potential of the region to serve its own internal priorities.

The China-Uzbekistan relations

The China-Uzbekistan relations are characterized by a wide spectrum of cooperation. A key milestone in the development of these relations was the state visit of the President of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, to China on May 25-27, 2005. During this visit, the Treaty of Friendly Cooperation and Partnership was signed between the two countries.

This treaty marked the transition of China-Uzbekistan relations to a new level of strategic partnership. It became the legal foundation for long-term cooperation in various areas, including politics, economy, culture, and security.

The signing of this treaty signified an important step in strengthening the comprehensive strategic partnership between China and Uzbekistan. It established a robust legal framework for further deepening the mutually beneficial cooperation between the two countries in the interests of their peoples.

In order to fully understand China's policy objectives and approach in this region, it would be necessary to conduct a more comprehensive examination of China's relations and interactions with each of the individual Central Asian countries that would be impacted by or involved in the "China - Kyrgyzstan - Uzbekistan" railway project. Such an analysis would shed light on the nuances of China's strategies and the broader geopolitical dynamics at play.

In 2013, China introduced the "Silk Road Economic Belt" (SREB) program, a blueprint for the economic development of Central Eurasia. This initiative subsequently evolved into China's global transit project, aimed at creating conditions and ensuring stable economic relations between the West and the East, primarily through the southern transit in Central Asia and to a lesser extent through the northern transit across Russian territory.

The investment cooperation between Uzbekistan and China has been steadily expanding in recent years, as evidenced by the growing number of Chinese companies establishing a presence in Uzbekistan. As of 2023, there are 347 enterprises with Chinese participation operating in the republic, of which 57 have 100% Chinese capital. Additionally, 64 representative offices of Chinese companies have been opened in Uzbekistan. Among the prominent Chinese firms with a foothold in the country are "SITIC," "China Machinery Corporation," "Huawei," and "Shanghai Bell."

Several major industrial projects undertaken with the involvement of Chinese expertise and investment have also been successfully implemented in Uzbekistan. The Kungrad Soda Plant and the Dehkanabad Potash Fertilizer Plant, both constructed with the participation of Chinese specialists, are now functioning efficiently and contributing to the country's economic development. Additionally, the modern high-speed electric locomotives supplied by the Zhuzhou Electric Locomotive Company have proven to be a valuable asset for Uzbekistan's transportation infrastructure.

The bilateral cooperation between Uzbekistan and China has also made significant strides in the energy sector. A notable example is the joint investment project for the construction of the "Uzbekistan-China" gas pipeline, which is currently underway with the involvement of Chinese partners.

Uzbekistan's strategic location has also made it a crucial link in the international transit railway corridor connecting China, Central Asia, and Europe. In 2016, the electrified railway line "Angren-Pap," spanning a total distance of over 120 kilometers, was completed at a cost of \$1.68 billion. Furthermore, the construction of the railway tunnel through the Kamchik Pass, undertaken by the Chinese company China Railway Tunnel Group, was a significant milestone in this regional connectivity project, with the project cost amounting to \$455 million.

Conclusion

Summarizing the examination of the fundamental stages in the evolutionary development of China's foreign policy doctrine, it is crucial to underscore that the modernization concept proposed by Deng Xiaoping served as the pivotal moment in this regard. This concept defined new orientations in the governance of the Chinese state. The idea of an "independent and autonomous foreign policy" was formulated, with the primary objective of accelerating China's economic development.

Essentially, the country renounced the expansionist ideas of Mao Zedong and embarked on a path of pragmatic policies aimed at enhancing China's foreign

economic significance on a global scale. Subsequent Chinese leaders advanced their own conceptual frameworks, which further deepened and effectively advanced the foundational principles laid out by Deng Xiaoping. For instance, the third generation of leaders headed by Jiang Zemin based their policies on the doctrine of a "new security system," which was subsequently carried forward in the political agenda of Hu Jintao (the fourth generation of Chinese leadership), who proposed to consider China's security directly contingent on the principles of "peaceful development."

The contemporary foreign policy orientation of China, which is encapsulated by the notion of the "Chinese Dream," merits particular attention. In the interpretation of the current leader, Xi Jinping, this concept implies the necessity for a Chinese foreign policy that not only enhances the country's global standing but also provides significant opportunities to significantly improve the living standards of the Chinese people.

It must be acknowledged, however, that the active foreign policy and foreign economic endeavors of the People's Republic of China have elicited decidedly equivocal assessments in international media outlets. The notion of a "China threat" is consistently perpetuated, which, according to Chinese experts, does not comport with reality, as the preservation of a peaceful global milieu remains a preeminent priority in China's contemporary foreign policy. Tangible manifestations of this orientation include multilateral diplomacy and developmental diplomacy. China actively participates in diverse international organizations and advances initiatives for the establishment of such organizations and international funds.

It bears reiteration that China's pragmatic and pacifist foreign policy, defined by the model of continuity with Deng Xiaoping's ideas, is primarily aimed at ensuring the prosperity of the Chinese populace, a goal that is reflected in the modern, multifaceted doctrine of the "Chinese Dream."

References:

1. Agreement between the Republic of Kazakhstan, the Kyrgyz Republic, the Russian Federation, the Republic of Tajikistan, and the People's Republic of China on Strengthening Trust in the Military Sphere in the Border Area, signed on April 26, 1996 <https://base.spinform.ru/>
2. Momonov, M.V. – (2007) The "Prevention of danger" strategy in China's foreign policy / International Trends (Russia). No. 3. - P. 28-43.

3. Wang Chaolin, Savkovich E.V. – (2018) The formation of a development belt in the Xinjiang Uygur Autonomous Region of the PRC in the early 2010s // Bulletin of Tomsk State University. History. - No. 55. - P. 95.

4. "Declaration on the Establishment of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization" (SCO), which was signed on June 15, 2001.

5. Cooley, A. (2012). Great Games, Local Rules: The New Great Power Contest in Central Asia. Oxford University Press.

6. Momonov M.V. - (2009) "The system of foreign policy priorities of modern China" – Moscow.